

Title: Analysing quantitative data for the ophthalmologist, the power of normal transformation; a novel calculator

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Abstract:

Purpose: Ophthalmology is a specialty rich in quantitative measurements which often do not follow a normal gaussian distribution. Normally distributed data is an important quality to enable parametric data analyses and confidence interval generation.

Parametric statistical tests are more powerful than their non-parametric equivalents but cannot be applied to non-normally distributed data without data transformation.

Methods: We have designed a novel calculator that performs automated transformation of data and provide a working example of how to perform normal transformation to enable conducting further parametric statistical analysis.

Results: Our calculator enables data transformations such as logarithmic, square, reciprocal, as well as more specialised tasks such as custom power, Templeton and automated Box-Cox transformation. It provides automated quantile-quantile (Q-Q) and histogram generation for each type of transformed data, allowing users to choose the most ideal transformation for their data in one step.

We include an overview on data transformation and demonstrate its utility through an example, to enable more clinicians and researchers to utilise this important technique.

Conclusion: Our novel calculator has the significant advantage to increase efficiency of data transformation through a commonly accessible software (Microsoft Excel).

Improving exposure and accessibility to these powerful statistical tools, the introduction of this calculator has the potential to enable more clinicians and researchers to utilise data transformation and, thus, set more robust research.

Keywords: ophthalmology, statistics, non-parametric statistical tests, normal transformation

Introduction

Ophthalmology is rich with quantitative data that are used clinically, as well as audit and research to report on baseline characteristics and outcomes. Important commonly reported quantitative measurements include, but are not limited to, visual acuity, intraocular pressure measurements, corneal topography, biometry measurements, visual field data and OCT findings such as central retinal thickness, and macular hole size.

What is a normal distribution?

A normal gaussian, bell-shaped distribution of continuous variables is an assumption of parametric statistical analyses. It allows the characteristics of the dataset to be described by just two variables, the mean and standard deviation (SD), and can be used to define confidence intervals (CI). Parametric statistics are more powerful tools to their non-parametric equivalent and are better able to test statistical hypothesis. Examples of parametric analyses include t-tests, analysis of variance (ANOVA), Pearson's product moment correlation and linear regression (in least square regression model, it is not the covariates are not required to carry a normal distribution but rather the residual errors) [1].

How to test normality of data?

There are many methods to determine whether data follow a normal distribution. Histograms and probability plots, such as quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plots, often provide a graphical representation of data distribution, although their interpretation is beyond the scope of this article. Furthermore, there are several descriptive statistical methods, such as examination of skew (ideally between -0.80 to 0.80) and kurtosis and their respective standard errors that shed light on data distribution [2]. More formal statistical analysis such as Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov Smirnov tests are commonly used to determine normality of data (at a p-value above the desired alpha (α) level, typically 0.05) that are available in most popular statistical software such as SPSS (IBM Corp, Armonk NY).

What is transforming of data?

Transformation of data involves modifying each data point with a specific calculation, therefore, changing the scale of measurement of the data and allowing the data to conform to a normal distribution, thus enabling employment of parametric statistics. For example, this could be taking the square or the logarithm of each datapoint, to achieve a normal distribution. As certain functions require non-zero or positive values (such as taking a square root), a translation of data can be performed. This involves adding a constant to each value so that all values are positive (Appendix 1). Normal transformation of data is an important methodology in statistical analyses that

ophthalmologists should know. A very common example within this field is the conversion of visual acuity from Snellen fraction and decimal visual acuity to Logarithm of the Minimum Angle of Resolution (logMAR) for statistical analysis. This is a form of logarithmic (log) transformation of data that allows for a more normal distribution, as Snellen fraction uses geometric progression, which is inherently skewed [3]. This article will introduce readers to common data transformations and explain how to use our included calculator to improve accessibility to powerful transformations.

Is a normal distribution required?

When there is evidence that the assumption of a normal distribution is not fulfilled, there are several options that do not require transformation of the variables. In certain situations, the use of parametric tests on non-normally distributed data is permitted; even if that is a departure from the assumptions of parametric tests and the test can still return reliable result [4]. For example, t-tests may be robust for non-normally distributed data in large samples or, in the case of two sample t-test of unequal population standard deviations, if the ratio of variance between groups is not more than two [4]. However, the input of a statistician should be sought prior to using parametric analysis on non-normally distributed data. Secondly, the use of non-parametric tests can be an alternative, that rely on the use of ranked data of the values, rather than their actual values and are therefore, 'distribution free' tests. However, although non-parametric tests have less assumptions than parametric tests, they are not assumption free. An example of when non-parametric test could be utilised is when performing statistical analyses on visual outcomes that include perception of light (PL) and no perception of light (NPL). As PL and NPL, have not been reliably and reproducibly converted to logMAR equivalent values and are commonly given numerical values to aid statistical analysis [3]. As these are numerical imputations to aid quantification in analysis of visual outcomes, we recommend avoiding parametric analysis and utilizing non-parametric analyses to interpret values as ordinal data [3].

Thirdly, additional more advanced techniques such as bootstrapping (repeated resampling of data) can be carried out that do not require the assumption of normality. Although these have several advantages, they are computationally intensive and require specialist subject knowledge [5].

Aside from some exceptions, such as with a logistic distribution, non-parametric tests are not as powerful as parametric tests (less likely to reject the null hypothesis if it is false), and do not produce CI (as parametric tests do), transformation of data is often performed so that data follow a more normal distribution. However, other statistical methods permit estimation of confidence intervals, such as the Hodges-Lehmann estimator or the aforementioned bootstrap in the absence of normally distributed data.

Transforming data to achieve normal distribution

It can be time consuming to find the correct transformations for each variable and subsequent analysis on transformed data to see if a normal distribution has been achieved. Therefore, we attach a supplementary Microsoft Excel® (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA) Worksheet (NormTransform.xlsx) that streamlines these calculations for the user. It performs common transformations (and necessary translations on data) to display relevant descriptive statistical metrics and respective Q-Q plots and histograms for each transformed data.

The ideal power to transform data is referred to as the ideal lambda (λ). The transformations included in our calculator include common transformations such as log transformation, several common power transformations (squaring, square root, reciprocal and custom λ) and also include more advanced transformation techniques such as Templeton transformation [6], and Box-Cox transformations [7]. Our calculator makes these analyses accessible to the reader, and they are performed automatically without further input from users other than to insert their data.

There are several free statistical packages that perform more complex data transformations. These include, but are not limited to, 'bestNormalize' (opensource R Package)[8], online based free calculator (R-based, but not available in English)[9]. Commercial software, such as MATLAB (Natick, Massachusetts: The MathWorks Inc.), Minitab (LLC, 2021. Minitab) or SPSS (IBM Corp, Armonk NY).

Types of data transformation

The type of transformation chosen depends on the skew/distribution of data, and the ease of interpretation following its transformation. All calculations involved for data transformations are included in Appendix 1.

Logarithmic transformation

The most common departure from normal distribution is a positive skew among human populations [4], and as such logarithmic is most often used: $\log(x), x > 0$ (if there are zero or negative values, it is appropriate to add a constant to translate all values to ensure they are positive), (Appendix 1) [9]. The most common bases used for transformations are the natural log, $[\ln(x)]$ and $\log_{10}x$ transformations.

Power transformations

Different power transformations are helpful with different directions of skew. The most used power transformations are referred to as the ladders of power:

$\left(\dots, \frac{1}{x^2}, \frac{1}{x}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}, \log\{x\}, \sqrt{x}, x^1, x^2, \dots \right)$

\backslash Corresponding lambda (λ) for the powers:

$\left(-2, -1, 0.5, \log \left(x \right), 0.5, 1, 2, \dots \right)$ As $x_0=1$, this is replaced with $\left(\log(x) \right)$

Reciprocal (inverse) transformation involves taking the inverse of data values for non-zero data $\left(\frac{1}{x}, \text{quad } x \neq 0 \text{ right}\right)$. This transformation is effective for positively skewed data, whereas higher powers (or λ) such as the square or cube transformations, are useful to transform negatively skewed data. With reciprocal transformations, as they reverse the order of the rank of the data, it is recommended to reflect the transformed data by multiplying the transformed data by -1. Some power transformations (all roots involving even numbers, such as the square root) are not possible for negative values, ($x < 0$), and a translation of data is required as described in Appendix 1. Our calculator will automatically choose a constant to translate data with and this is displayed in the output table. As well as performing common power transformations, the calculator allows for a custom power transformation. This may not be possible in the case of powers incompatible with non-zeros and negative numbers (such as even roots) and will output an error if the input data are incompatible. Users are free to add their own constant to translate data as well.

Box-Cox Transformation

First described in 1967 by Box and Cox et al., [7] this is an advanced transformation method that involves finding the ideal power (λ) to transform data to achieve the most normal distribution. The relevant calculations are found in Appendix 1 [7].

As x_1 is the original data, if λ is close to 1, the original data most likely does not require transformation. However, though the ideal λ may achieve the best normal distribution, it may not be the most appropriate transformation. Choosing the closest lambda that achieves normality, on the ladders of power (Appendix 1) often leads to data that is easier to interpret. For example, if the ideal λ is 0.465 then it would make more sense to use $\lambda = 0.5$ and performing a square root transformation of the data. As such our Excel sheet not only reports on the ideal λ , but on the lower and upper closest λ to the ladders of power, as well as allowing for a custom λ value.

Templeton Transformation

The Templeton transformation cannot be performed in a single calculation. Step one involves converting data to the percentile rank to achieve uniformity and generates a set of uniform probabilities. The second step is for transformation to normal [6]. These calculations have been adopted from Templeton et al. The limitation of this transformation is that original data must be continuous and low numbers of levels in an ordinal data (such as a five or seven point Likert scaled responses) will achieve little difference to distribution using this transformation [6]. To ensure correct interpretation of transformed data, a statistician is recommended. The details of the calculations are found in Appendix 1.

Materials and Methods

Using the calculator

The calculator (NormTransform.xlsx) is available for download as supplementary material attached to this manuscript.

This worksheet has been designed to be compatible with Microsoft Excel 2010 onwards (except for the automated histogram charts, requiring Excel 2016 onwards. N.B. other spreadsheet software such as Google Sheets may not generate automated histograms and therefore the .xlsx file should be downloaded and opened in Microsoft Excel). It is compatible with a dataset of 10,000 data entries although can run slow depending on computational power. We must emphasise this spreadsheet is not intended to replace mainstream statistical software for normal transformations, but to quickly highlight whether the original data are normally distributed, and which common transformations would be effective in the presented data. Additionally, this reports on the ideal λ in Box-Cox transformations that requires multiple steps in most statistical software; usually beyond the expertise of a physician. The input required is to paste or input data into column A, starting from cell A2 (Supplementary Figure 1A). We advise to utilise special paste as values function to maintain the appearance of the original spreadsheet. All transformed data are presented in the green columns between columns B to L in real-time. Any gaps in the data are not supported and will result in errors. All customisable or editable cells are coloured light blue. There is a Green to Red colour scale of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) with transformed data and normalised z-scores as an estimate for normal distribution ($r=1$ being the most likely to have a normal distribution) in the output table (Supplementary Figure 1B). This should be used in combination with skew, standard error of skew, kurtosis, median, mean, Q-Q plots and histograms to estimate normality. Example output of automatically produced Q-Q plots and histograms are found in Supplementary Figure 2.

Results

Working example

In Supplementary Figure 1 we include fictional intraocular pressure measurements in the blue column (section A). The original data is not normally distributed as is clear by the histogram and Q-Q plot in Supplementary Figure 2 (input data, top left). The following green columns in Supplementary Figure 1A include all the transformed data. Supplementary Figure 1B is the analysis of the transformed data. All columns highlighted in yellow are recommended by the worksheet as appropriate transformations to achieve a normal transformation. This shows that the logarithmic,

and the Box-Cox transformation are appropriate transformations. The Box-Cox algorithm found that an ideal λ of -0.28 and the lower boundary of -0.50 (closest on the ladder of powers) achieved the most normal distribution. However, as log transformations are easier to work with, this is recommended in the first instance. All these solutions would work as is verified in Supplementary Figure 2 with normal distribution for logarithmic, Box-Cox (ideal λ) and Box-Cox (lower λ). The transformed data (Supplementary Figure 1A) can be directly copied, and can now be used with parametric tests, such as independent t-tests.

Finally, this database is not limited to use by ophthalmologists and is compatible with any continuous data.

Discussion

Our calculator provides an efficient and accessible tool for data transformation for users that may not have formal statistical experience. This is a free tool that seamlessly integrates with commonly used spreadsheet workflows such as Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Available from: <https://office.microsoft.com/excel>), ensuring ease of use without programming expertise.

Clinical Relevance and Impact on Research

Research in clinical fields such as Ophthalmology rely on the handling of skewed quantitative measures such as intraocular pressure, visual acuity and central retinal thickness. The ability to apply appropriate transformations ensures the validity of parametric tests and prevents misleading conclusions due to violations of normality assumptions [10]. Inappropriate handling of non-normally distributed data can lead to incorrect p-value and confidence interval calculations, further resulting in inappropriate clinical research conclusions [11]. In providing an accessible and user friendly tool for transformation of data, our calculator enhances the ability of researchers to complete robust statistical analyses which can translate into more precise and reliable findings in clinical research.

Potential Misuse and Considerations

While transformation of data may improve the robustness of statistical results when using parametric statistical tests, caution must be exerted in interpretation of results with careful consideration of clinical significance. In the example displayed in Supplementary Figure 1, transformed intraocular pressure data may achieve normality which can then be applied to a parametric statistical test that proves statistical significance. Researchers must acknowledge that the data has been transformed and this data may not be as clinically significant as raw intraocular pressure values [12].

Large Sample Considerations

Our calculator is able to transform up to 10,000 data entries, but larger datasets may face computational restrictions with Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Available from: <https://office.microsoft.com/excel>). Furthermore, for sufficiently large sample sizes, parametric tests may remain valid statistical tests even where the normality of outcome variables is not achieved and transformation of data may not always be necessary [13]. Advanced techniques such as bootstrapping may be necessary for complex statistical interpretation, beyond simple transformation and application of parametric tests [14].

Future directions

Our calculator currently supports single-sample data transformations. Two-samples would require each sample to be transformed separately. Future enhancements could include automated multi-group transformations which would facilitate more complex study designs. Additionally integration with commercially available statistical software or automation through machine learning could further enhance data analysis through recommending the most suitable transformation based on the input data characteristics [6].

Conclusion

Our novel calculator has the significant advantage to increase efficiency of data transformation through a commonly accessible software (Excel). Improving exposure and accessibility to these powerful statistical tools, the introduction of this calculator has the potential to enable more clinicians and researchers to utilise data transformation and, thus, set more robust research.

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Supporting information

-**Data transformation calculator:** Excel sheet NormTransform.xlsx

-**Appendix 1**

-**Supplementary Figure 1: Calculator input and output**

(A) Input column in blue (use paste as values function). Data gaps are not supported. Output columns (transformed data) in green.

(B) Table of analysis of transformed data. Correlation with expected Normal represents a Pearson correlation with standardised z-scores. This colour scale is relative to the rest of the transformations and green does not mean the data are normally distributed following transformation. Other metrics such as skew, standard error of skew and kurtosis, histograms and quantile-quantile plots should be used to determine normality. In this instance, a logarithmic transformation is sufficient to achieve normality. Transformations with skew between -1 and 1 are highlighted in yellow in the table as possible appropriate transformations.

-**Supplementary Figure 2: Example of transformed data quantile-quantile plots and histograms generation in calculator.**

These are automatically generated Q-Q plots and histograms following input of data.

Useful transformations are identifiable at a glance; in this instance, logarithmic and

Templeton transformations would be appropriate. However, the reciprocal, square root and square transformations are ineffective at producing normally distributed data.